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INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article is about innovative ways to teach foreign language to young students. Tips on how to understand various complex terms.

Key words: Modern methods, innovative methods, clear facts, evidence.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first grades of secondary schools from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of continuous training is proof of this. Nowadays, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students of M.T.M. and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in mastering the achievements of world science and development. Language learning also depends on age periods. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest. Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way:

- to teach by means of songs and poems the letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember, that do not have meaning.

For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

- games related to mental and physical activities;

- cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.
- role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: if one student shows howling of a dog and meowing of a cat, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.
- subject environment; if the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, children will learn the language better. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) will give. This hoi strengthens students' vocabulary, language abilities, and expands their worldview.
- riddles; children have a strong interest in finding answers to riddles. Therefore, when the teacher says the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to say the answer in English. Then children learn words quickly.
- practical training (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "A teacher who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should use as many of the child's sensory organs as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations, and even if if possible, he should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering". For example: when a teacher tastes an apple, its color is red or green, He should give information about the smell of sweet (tasty) or sour (), fragrant () and feed the fruits to other students and ask them to give information about that fruit in English. it also helps in their further learning. If the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the time when he ate the fruit, he quickly remembers that it is red-red, green-green. So, using such a method helps the student's information in the long-term memory ensures that it remains.
- through gestures, facial expressions; When the teacher says something to the child or gives an order, for example, it is understandable to the child if he uses gestures in sentences such as come here, open the book, stand up, look at the blackboard. . - through visual aids, posters, books; - writing on things that are visible and often used in everyday life. For example: writing on a door, book,

table, blackboard, window, etc. Since such things are always visible and often used in practice, the child learns these words involuntarily.

- through news; We know that children are curious. They quickly get bored with the sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them not always using the same methods, but to change and update such methods. Otherwise, children will understand how the teacher will teach and prepare for it. Teaching with innovative methods raises children's aspirations.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should be conducted as an interesting activity, not as a duty, and learning using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. It is necessary to explain to children how important it is to learn foreign languages through natural conditions. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi knew many foreign languages perfectly, was able to speak them easily and created in them. Such an opportunity motivated scholars to study world science and do great things. After all, as our grandfather Navoi said, "He who knows the language knows the world."

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